

Fabrication of Continuous Carbon Nanotube Fibers

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1. Experimental

Carbon nanotubes (CNTs) are well known as a remarkable material for high strength, high aspect ratio, high electrical conductivity, high thermal conductivity and field emission property. Due to these excellent properties, CNTs can be applied to field emission device (FED), composite materials, actuator and other fields.[1-2]

Fabrication of CNTs into fibers is an important challenge in order to apply CNTs to much wider range fields. Recently, many different methods for CNT fibers have been reported such as 'Coagulation method', 'Spinning from a nanotube mat', Liquid-crystal spinning' and 'Direct growth of CNT fibers'.[2-5]

In this work, we prepared CNT fibers by Chemical vapor deposition (CVD) method and investigated the effects of post-processing on the CNT fibers.

2. Experimental

2.1. Materials

Ferrocene and thiophene, CNT catalyst and activator, were obtained from Sigma Aldrich Korea. Acetone and Dimethyl sulfoxide (DMSO) were purchased from Samchun Chemical.

2.2. Spinning

A solution of Ferrocene (1~2wt%) and thiophene (0.3~12wt%) dispersed in acetone injected into furnace (8~15ml/hr) with hydrogen gas (800~1200 sccm) like Fig.1.

A tubular web of CNTs was formed within the furnace and drawn out from the furnace to the

bottom of water bath. Morphology of the CNT web changed to fiber form while passing through the water bath.

2.3. Post-processing

The CNT fibers were post-treated in two ways, which were shrinking treatment using organic solvent and polymer coating method. The post-treated CNT fibers were dried and wound onto a roller.

Fig. 1. CVD synthesis set-up for manufacturing of continuous CNT fibers.

3. Results

3.1. Property

The CNT fibers, which had 10~20 μ m diameter, were highly flexible as much as it can be knotted as

shown in Fig. 2. To make condensed CNT fibers acetone and DMSO were used, which are known to shrink CNT assembly. After condensing the CNT fibers, density and mechanical properties were much enhanced. In addition, electrical conductivity increased 10 times than before. The CNT fibers were coated with polymer solutions such as PVA/DMSO or PAN/DMSO. The tensile strength of polymer coated CNT fibers increased 2 or 3 times compared to uncoated CNT fibers. However, the breaking elongation decreased. Fig.3. shows that the surface of CNT fibers became compact by solvent treatment and smooth by polymer coating.

Fig. 2. SEM images of (a) neat, (b) knotted, (c) two-ply and (d) multi-ply CNT fibers.

Fig.3. SEM images of (a) neat, (b) acetone shrunken and (c) PVA coated CNT fibers surface.

3.2. Thermal gravity analysis (TGA)

The CNT synthesized here was thermally analyzed with TGA. As shown in Fig.4, CNT contents was about 90~92wt% and 8~10wt% impurities, which were metal catalysts and amorphous carbon.

Fig.4. Thermal gravity analysis (TGA) curve of CNT fiber measured under nitrogen atmosphere.

References

- [1] Xiao-Hua Zhong, Ya-Li Li and Ya-Kun Liu “Continuous Multilayered Carbon Nanotube Yarns”, *Advanced materials*, Vol. 21, pp1-5, 2009.
- [2] Ya-Li Li, Ian A. Kinloch and Alan H. Windle, “Direct Spinning of Carbon Nanotube Fibers from Chemical Vapor Deposition Synthesis”, *Science*, Vol. 304, pp276-278, 2004.
- [3] Kai Liu, Yinghui Sun, Ruifeng Zhou and Hanyu Zhu “Carbon nanotube yarns with high tensile strength made by a twisting and shrinking method”, *Nanotechnology*, Vol. 21, pp045708-045714, 2010
- [4] Brigitte Vigolo, Alain Penicaud and Catherine Journet “ Macroscopic Fibers and Ribbons of Oriented Carbon Nanotubes”, *Science*, Vol. 290, pp1331-1334, 2000.
- [5] Lars M. Ericson, Hua Fan and Richard E. Smalley “Macroscopic, Neat, Single-Walled Carbon Nanotube Fibers”, *Science*, Vol. 305, pp1447-1450, 2004.
- [6] Marcelo Motta, Ian Kinloch and Anna Moisala “The parameter space for the directspinning of fibres and films of carbon nanotubes”, *Physica E*, Vol. 37, pp40-43, 2007.
- [7] Kai Liu, Yinghui Sun and Kili Jiang “Scratch-Resistant, Highly Conductive, and High-Strength Carbon Nanotube-Based Composite Yarns”, *ACS Nano*, Vol. 4, No. 10, pp5827-5834, 2010